

COMPARATIVE CLASSIFICATION OF COMPOUND SENTENCES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: When defining a compound sentence, some English scholars have it and focus on the number of cuts, some focus on the number of simple sentences in the compound sentence, and still others combine the two. The theory of compound sentences in English was fully formed in English normative grammar in the second half of the 19th century and has remained unchanged to this day. This article discusses the comparative analysis of English compound sentences in Uzbek.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, at a time when international dialogue and relations are wide open, translations of English compound sentences are developing. This is evidenced by the fact that English phrases and words have entered the Uzbek and other languages. Learning English is a topical issue for Uzbek youth today. This issue, which is still relevant today, was on the agenda of our ancient ancestors. For example, Farobi knew more than seventy languages, Osman Nasir translated an entire work by heart, and Navoi and other scholars wrote in two languages.¹

MAIN PART

In the following examples, we will look at the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek compound sentences, the contextual relationship between them, and the word order in sentences in two languages:

¹ G‘apparov M. «Ingilz tili grammatikasi» Toshkent 2006. 336 p.

«*The city was very nice and our flat was very fine*» - "*Shahar juda chiroyli edi va bizning kvartiramiz juda yaxshi edi*".

The compound sentence in English has been translated into Uzbek as a compound sentence without a conjunction. In the English compound sentence, "The city" is the owner of the first sentence, and "was" is the participle of "and", which connects two simple sentences, the determinant, "flat" is the owner of the second sentence, "was very fine."

By the 1970s, while studying compound sentences, Ilish had explored the main differences based on which clause they were related to. According to the scholar, some compound sentences are connected by a connecting word according to their function and its meaning is determined, while others do not require such words when connected. A conjunction is a synonym that is not a conjunction. However, the scientist calls both of them a compound sentence because they contain several components.²

The English scholar Ilish at that time considered the problem of converting homogeneous parts into compound sentences. He said, "I met my relatives and friends would be said to have been 'contracted' out of two sentences: 'I met my relatives, and I met my friends'".³

There are two bases in the study of sentence, which is one of the components of language, in particular, in the study of conjunctions:

- a) the basis of having widespread popularity;
- b) by the way, the basis of the cut with a number of exceptions.

The first direction is based on and connected with the modern doctrine of simple speech. With the doctrine of European linguistics, which re-acquired this direction in the middle of the twentieth century, that a sentence must consist of two parts, that there can be no ownerless sentences, the judgment of logic consists of two

² Ganshina M.A. Vasilevskaya N.M. «English grammar» M., Higher school publishing house 1964 598 p.

³ Ilish B. «The structure of Modern English» Leningrad 1971. 366 p.

parts - the subject and the predicate. consisted of the doctrine of the subordination of the subject and the subordination of the predicate.

Subject clause

“What was important to him was matrimony”- *“Uning uchun muhim bo’lgan narsa nikoh edi”*. "What was important to him" is the following sentence, "was matrimony" is the main sentence. We define this by asking questions, because the question is always asked from the main sentence, and the subordinate clause is determined by determining which part of the sentence is in the main sentence, interpreting and completing it.

Predicative clause

«The fact was, she did not understand us» - *“Shu aniqki, u bizni tushunmadi”*.

In this example, "the fact was" is the main sentence, "she did not understand us" is the participle.

Object clause

“I don’t know what he is talking about” – *“U nima haqida gapirayotganini bilmayman”*.

In this example, "I don't know" is the main sentence.

Attributive clause

«The woman who was here yesterday is a tailor» - *“Kecha bu yerda bo’lgan ayol tikuvchi edi”*.

In this example, "The woman is a tailor" is the preposition, followed by the pronoun "who was here yesterday" which defines the word "the woman" in the preposition.

Translation difficulties are not limited to linguistic differences. Sometimes the problem of translating from a new language is more complicated than from a long language. Although the languages to be translated or to be translated are lexically-grammatically and structurally distant from each other, the problem of translation is that if they feel similarity, commonality, harmony, commonality in terms of subject,

literary tradition, stage of cultural development of two languages the possibility of a successful solution arises.

Language is one of the most important indicators of a work of art. In translation, this main factor changes, one language is replaced by another, and as the language changes, there is sometimes a phenomenon of methodological shift. In many cases, the interpreter himself consciously allows this to happen, using it as a precaution.

«I hope he's not ill» - «Ishqilib betob emasmi?»

According to AV Fedorov, “translators often face the problem of reflecting the rhythm of translation in the translation of prose works. However, this feature, reflected in the work of each writer, is based on the lexical-phonetic, grammatical-structural means of the language, which in the process of translation should not be copied blindly. In translation, each writer's style must be re-created, taking into account the capabilities and characteristics of the other language. ”

Conjunctions used in English are not essentially different from conjunctions used in other languages. There is a lot of artistic style in the use of compound sentences. It is also interesting that the content relations are presented in different languages by the same device or by another device, as well as the material in which the sections are expressed in English and Uzbek. The content expressed in English sources is not always available in Uzbek versions.

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